

The Colossal Buddha at Aukana

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ONE OF THE MOST impressive monuments among the many that reflect the glory of ancient Ceylon, is an immense image of the Buddha, carved from the face of a great rock at an ancient monastic site which bears the modern name of Aukana. This tiny vihāra is situated in a clearing deep in the jungle of north-central Ceylon some distance southwest of Anurādhapura. Nearby is a vast artificial lake, the Kalāveva, which is associated in Ceylon's history with the names of the fifth century rulers of Lankā. A small group of monks still attend the image and keep the modern vihāra attached to it.

Fig. 1. The Buddha at Aukana.

Fig. 2. Detail of the Buddha, Figure 1.

The giant Buddha at Aukana (Fig. 1) was one of the earliest Sinhalese Buddha images of colossal size. Its immense form rises to a height of about forty-three feet and it is carved almost completely in the round. The Buddha is shown standing in the *samabhangā* position with the *uttarāsangā* draped leaving the right shoulder bare and with the loose end falling over the left shoulder and arm and hanging free down to the ankles. The right hand is raised in the *abhaya mudrā*, but with the hand itself held at right angles to the shoulder. The left arm is bent holding the robe, and the hand, at shoulder level, is closed and held with the back of the fist facing outward. The middle fingers are more tightly clenched than the outer ones and the hand does not grasp the robe. The figure stands on a pedestal, the front of which has been carved in the form of a double-lotus. The flame-shape which crowns the *usbnisha* is a later addition and this feature was probably not part of the original design.

The projection of the pedestal was not carved out of the living rock, but was made separately and then pushed into place. Behind it, and below the feet of the image, is a natural cavity in the rock within which there was fashioned a small square chamber whose sides and bottom were formed by slabs of stone. Within this small chamber there had been placed bronze images of Brahmā and the brahmanical gods of the four directions.¹ The arrangement was clearly intended as a cosmograph above which towers the giant form of the Buddha.

The colossal image faces due east and was initially enclosed within a rectangular shrine (Fig. 2) built against the face of the rock from which the image is carved; the shrine is entered from the east. The lower part of the building has been preserved and its massive stone walls give us a clear idea of the original shape.

Internally, the shrine consisted of an image chamber, or *garbha-griha*, which measured about twenty-five feet by fifty feet. Around this chamber, on the three free sides, there was a continuous aisle or ambulatory. The inner and outer doors were in the center of the eastern wall. That portion of the shrine above the preserved stone walls was built of brick; wedge-shaped bricks, found in the ruins of the building, suggest that the roof was vaulted. Immediately opposite the entrance is another hummock of granite against which stairs were once built to

provide direct access to the image house. The remains of no other major buildings have been found in the area although remnants can be seen nearby of some undistinguished structures probably made much later from the ruins of the image house.

The colossal Buddha at Aukana may be the earliest of a great many colossi culminating in the celebrated group at Polonnaruva, the Gal Vihāra.² In a general sense, there is no doubt that the colossal type of Buddha image was inspired by Mahāyānistic theology.³ In a very specific way, the Buddha of Aukana embodies the Mahāyānistic concept of the transmundane quality of the Buddha.

The giant form, looming motionless above the double-lotus on which it stands, may be understood to express the cosmic character of the divine personality. The lotus contains within it the cosmographically disposed images of the directional gods and may be thought of as the Universe, All-Space, within which are contained Heaven and Earth and all phenomenal things. The Buddha towers above the macrocosmic lotus as *Lokottara*, transcending and beyond (*uttara*) the spheres of the world (*loka*).

Lokottaravāda was the cardinal doctrine of the Mahāsaṅghika sect and brings to mind the distinguishing belief in an eternal and unmanifest Buddha which Buddhaghosa attributed to the eclectic and heterodox sectarians of the *Vetullavāda*.⁴

The disposition of the giant figure within what is symbolically a square sanctum surrounded by an ambulatory path, equates the image, liturgically, with the stūpa; the ritual and cyclic progression, inherent in the circumambulation, invests the image, appropriately, with the character of eternal time.

A similar image-house, with the shattered remains of a colossal and freestanding Buddha image, has been found at Māligavela,⁵ in Uva province. The shrine here, made of brick, measured, in plan, about seventy-two feet square. The remains of the Buddha image measure around thirty-four feet and have been mutilated by time and treasure-hunters, so that very little of its original appearance can be reconstructed. But the image and its shrine, being freestanding, represent the kind of arrangement which the Aukana image and shrine intended to suggest.⁶

Fig. 3. Buddha images in the *pilima-ge* at Medirigiriya.

At Puliyankulama *vihāra*, all that remains of a colossal standing Buddha image are the broken lotus pedestal and fragments of a massive stone *yantragala*. Here, as at Aukana, the ordinary cosmic symbolism of the lotus had been invested with a theological specification by means of symbolic deposits within the compartmented stone. The *yantragala*, properly informed by signs and symbols, became the diagrammatic equivalent of the Universe; the lotus enshrining the cosmograph became all of the worlds; the image towering above became the Transcendent One.

The same devices are used to convey the concept of transcendence in a triad of Buddha images in the *pilima-ge* at Medirigiriya,⁷ (Fig. 3) which are large in size, but not colossal. Beneath the lotus pedestal of each image is a stone *yantragala* of twenty-five chambers in which were deposited auspicious and precious objects, including the figures of animals . . . bull, lion, elephant, horse . . . associated symbolically with the four directions. Beneath the *yantragala* of the central image, a brick-lined pit was fashioned to contain the deposit of a conch-shell. In this way, the cell below the cosmographic *yantragala* was defined as the primordial waters, the support of the universe.

These images do not overwhelm by virtue of sheer size; yet they operate symbolically to realise the *lokottara* nature of the Buddha.

At Buduruwegala,⁸ in the jungle southwest of Vellavāya, seven colossal images are carved in relief on the face of a great rock. The group consists of Bodhisattva triads to the right and

Fig. 4. The Buddha at Buduruwegala.

Fig. 5. The Buddha at Sesseruva.

left of a central Buddha,⁹ (Fig. 4) which is in a ruinous condition. The seven icons, hierarchically arranged by size, are disposed along the face of the rock from which they are cut like a giant *mandala*, thrice-operative. The feet and pedestals of the Buddha figure and those of the middle bodhisattvas were separately carved and joined to the main rock. Although there is no indication of cosmographic symbols having been deposited within the pedestals, there is no doubt that the spectacular size of these images was intended to express the *lokottara* nature of their being.¹⁰

Another colossal Buddha (Fig. 5), was carved like the Aukana example, from the living rock, at Sesseruva in the North Central Province.¹¹ The image dominates an ancient monastery built against the southern cliff of Mahā-kanda. Over thirty-nine feet tall, it is cut in high relief in the scarp wall of the hill and shows the Buddha standing within a hollow of rock, one hand raised in the *abhaya* mudrā, palm out, and the other poised, holding the robe, exactly like its counterpart at Aukana. The lotus pedestal of this image was never finished. Grooves and mortices in the rock and the remnants of pillars in the site in front of the image are all that remain of the shrine which once enclosed it.

The colossal Buddha of Aukana, it is clear, represents a type of Mahāyāna Buddha image

Fig. 6. Bronze torso in the Madras Government Museum.

that was popular in Ceylon during the medieval period.¹² It combines perfectly the expressive elements of scale and iconography, and it remains the principal expression of the *Lokottara* theme in Sinhalese art.

The Buddha of Aukana was first noticed, in recent times, by Bell who mentioned it in his celebrated report of 1895 for the Archaeological Survey of Ceylon.¹³ Burrows, in his "Buried Cities of Ceylon"¹⁴ connected it with the Kalāveva in the direction of which it faces. Vincent Smith reproduced a photograph of it and remarked that local tradition considered it a work of the time of Parākramabahu I (1153-1186 A.D.).¹⁵ Coomaraswamy¹⁶ dated it in the thirteenth century and considered it an excellent example of what he called the "late Sinhalese style."

In 1949, the Archaeological Department undertook the conservation of the site¹⁷ and at that time, Paranavitana associated the image with the Kalāveva and dated both the image and the shrine in the late fifth century, when Dhātusena enlarged the Kalāveva.¹⁸

In 1952, a mason, working at Aukana, discovered a donative inscription on a granite slab which was built into the northern wall of the shrine.¹⁹ This inscription was written in Sinhalese characters which may be dated in the eighth

Fig. 7. Limestone fragment from Pidurāgala.

century. The image house, then, must date from sometime in the eighth century.

The image, however, may date from that time or earlier. Paranavitana, in his report²⁰ on the inscription and date, insisted that the Buddha image is considerably earlier than the shrine and reasserted his prior assumption of a fifth century date for the image.

This assumption, of course, was based on the supposition that the finest Buddha images in Ceylon of pre-Polonaruva date were made during the third, fourth, and fifth centuries and that little of any artistic consequence was produced during the "dark ages" between that heyday of Anurādhapura culture and the "renaissance" of Parākramabahu I. Moreover, the Aukana colossus manifests the obvious characteristics of the Amarāvati-Anurādhapura style together with some so-called "Gupta"²¹ qualities which might make a fifth century date seem inevitable.

The question of the date of this image must be settled on the basis of an analysis of its style and in relation to the development of sculptural style in the Buddhist art of Ceylon from the fifth century to the eighth.

I have said earlier that the Aukana Buddha manifests the obvious and distinguishing characteristics of the Amarāvati style. The typical Buddha image in the Amarāvati style is characterized by a strict frontality and heavy massive form. The shapes of the body are broadly and simply fashioned. Their surfaces are subtly articulated to animate the form; yet the shapes

Fig. 8. Limestone fragment from Pidurāgala.

beneath the drapery are scarcely revealed through it. The *uttarāsanga* is draped leaving the right shoulder bare and the loose end hangs from the left arm to the ankles. The drapery folds run obliquely across the body in an ordered rhythm of incised lines yet with both regularity and variety in the placement and intervals. A heavy billowing fold in the robe near the ankles is a distinguishing feature.

The width of the shoulders and hips are roughly the same and the curve of the body contour is not emphasized nor accentuated. The common *mudrās* are the *abhaya* for the right hand with the left hand held shoulder high, closed, and with its back facing forward.

A good example of the Sinhalese version of this style is the limestone Buddha from the terrace of the Mahāthūpa in Anurādhapura,²² which may be dated in the fourth or fifth century.²³

In the Aukana image, the Amarāvātī style is apparent in the manner of wearing the *uttarāsanga*, in the billowing fold, in the *mudrās*, and to a certain extent in the general disposition of the drapery folds. The form, however, is de-

cidely more full and fleshy. The shapes of the body are clearly distinguished beneath the drapery and the line where the lower garment presses into the abdomen is emphatically rendered (Fig. 2). Moreover, the drapery lines are more finely drawn by a succession of concavities which meet in crisp and sharp ridges. They are closely and regularly spaced and accent the contours of the anatomy beneath. The shoulders are markedly broader than the hips and the details of the face—brow, nose, and lips—show sharp edges. The eyes are half closed. These qualities differentiate the Aukana Buddha from the Amarāvātī style and relate it, superficially at least, to the “Gupta” style of North India.

There is sufficient evidence, institutional, inscriptional, and literary, for the continued intercourse between the religious centers of Magadha and Ceylon. Sinhalese monks are known to have flourished at Bodh Gayā under the patronage of Gupta kings and we have records of Sinhalese pilgrims making the rounds of the holy places of Magadha. It seems reasonable, then, to suppose that through such contact, the “Gupta” style was introduced to Ceylon and the result was the transformation of the Amarāvātī-Anurādhapura style sometime in the fifth century.

However, recent scholarship, and more recent excavation, have proven that the coalescence of the “Gupta” style with that of Amarāvātī came about in the Krishna valley itself when the Āndhradeśa experienced a revival of Buddhist culture under the patronage of the Eastern Chālukyas. The center of this renaissance was apparently Amarāvātī, where the new excavations have revealed sculptures and shrines of eighth, ninth and tenth century date.

Douglas Barrett, in a study published in *Art and Letters*,²⁴ has defined a “Later School of Amarāvātī” which flourished in the Āndhradeśa from the seventh through the tenth centuries, when the area was under the political domination of the Eastern Chālukyas.

Among the sculptures which he has attributed to this time are two groups of bronze Buddhas which were found at Amarāvātī²⁵ and Buddha-pad.²⁶ Some of these exhibit the externals of the “Gupta” style in the tall, slender bodies with broad shoulders and narrow waists, in the thin smooth and transparent robes revealing the body beneath, and in the clearly emphasized line of the undergarment across the abdomen.

The common *mudrā* for this group is the *varada* for the right hand. But the *abhaya mudrā* is also used, with the hand held at right angles to the body.

This type of Buddha image is frequently found in North India and was most popular in the northwest Deccan from which region it may have passed to the valley of the Krishna River sometime in the sixth or seventh century.

Others of these Āndhra bronzes manifest generally the earlier style of Amarāvati with the exceptions that the robe reveals the shapes of the body beneath, the figure is less massive, more slender, and the line of the contour of the body is more pronounced as is the difference in width between the shoulders and thighs. Moreover, the *vitarka mudrā* is commonly displayed in the right hand. Barrett dates the bronzes of this second group in the late seventh and eighth centuries.

A striking example of this type, in the Madras Government Museum (Fig. 6) and dated by Barrett around 700 A.D., clearly demonstrates the transformation of the early style of Amarāvati under the impact of the "Gupta" style of the North.

If we combine the general style characteristics of the second group of Āndhra bronzes with the variant of the *abhaya mudrā* found in some of the first group, we will produce an imaginary type of Buddha which is very much like the colossal image of Aukana. And if we date this imagined type of Buddha image in the eighth century, along with most of those in Barrett's second group, we have arrived at a date which coincides perfectly with that of the image-house of the Buddha at Aukana.

Since the art of Amarāvati had been the inspiration for Sinhalese Buddhists in the third and fourth centuries, we may reasonably assume that it retained its prestige and was the source from which Ceylon derived the new and hybrid style of the Buddha of Aukana. If the new form of the Amarāvati Buddha was invented in the Āndhradeśa toward the late seventh century, then similar forms in Ceylon cannot date much before 700 A.D. The colossal Buddha of Aukana, then, must date from the eighth century and must be contemporary with the image-house which once enclosed it and of which the lower walls remain.

The theory that the style of the Later School of Amarāvati was extended to Ceylon is given

considerable support by evidence found in Ceylon itself. A number of fragments have been found, in Ceylon, of carved limestone of that type which is common in the Krishna valley and not local to Ceylon.

The most important of these finds is a group of relief fragments which were taken from the eighth century relic chamber of the stūpa at Pidurāgala,²⁷ near Sigiriya. The group consists of a fragment showing a row of Buddhas (Fig. 7), another with a row of Bodhisattvas (Fig. 8), and a badly broken slab depicting a Buddha wreathed in flames, with attendants and adoring figures (unfortunately not illustrated).

The type of the Buddha figures in the first fragment seems to be very much like that of the Early School of Amarāvati except that the waist is more slender and the curve of the body contour is more pronounced. The bodhisattva figures, though blackened and rubbed, manifest elements of Chālukya style and costume. And the bodhisattvas display the *vitarka* and *kataka mudrās*. The same combination of gestures is shown by the Buddha in the flame mandorla. And in this Buddha figure, the shape of the legs shows through the robe.

These slabs must represent the first essays in the Eastern Chālukya style of Amarāvati and must date from the late seventh or early eighth century. They may have been carved in the Āndhradeśa and imported to Ceylon for enshrinement in the stūpa at Pidurāgala. Or Amarāvati limestone may have been regarded as venerable in Ceylon and a Sinhalese craftsman trained at Amarāvati, or an artisan from Āndhradeśa imported to Ceylon may have carved the slabs.

Another Amarāvati limestone relief (Fig. 9) was found at Girihanduvihāra, near Ambalan-tota. The subject matter represented is not known but the type of the Buddha figure corresponds to that of Barrett's first bronze style group, except for the detail of the *uttarāsanga* hem running from the shoulder to the ankle. I have not seen this feature on a standing Buddha figure anywhere, but it appears commonly on seated Buddhas which may be dated after the middle of the eighth century. The combination of mudrās corresponds to that associated by Barrett with the second Āndhra bronze style group.

These sculptured slabs, carved from Amarāvati limestone and enshrined in Ceylon, underscore the connections existent between Ceylon

Fig. 9. Limestone slab from Girihanduvihāra.

Fig. 10. Buddha image from the Thūpārāma, Polonnaruva.

Fig. 11. Limestone torso in the Colombo Museum.

and the Āndhradeśa at a time when that region was experiencing a second great moment in her history.

The Buddha of Aukana is one of a number of Sinhalese Buddha images which manifest the style of the Later School of Amarāvati.

The central Buddha of the *pīlima-ge* at Medirigiriya²⁸ (Fig. 3) conforms to the canons of the Early Amarāvati style, modified by the gentle indication of the body forms showing through the garment, by a slight fleshy swell at the waist and the mark of the undergarment, and by the regular and close disposition of the grooves which define the drapery folds. Yet the hip-waist-shoulder curve is not so accentuated and the depression between the legs is not deep.

Similar stone standing Buddhas are found in the large sculpture gallery of the Anurādhapura Museum and a corresponding type was found at the Thūpārāma of Polonnaruva (Fig. 10).²⁹ The bronze Buddhas of Dong Duong³⁰ and Korat,³¹ commonly called "import" bronzes,³² may be grouped with these stone images and regarded as Sinhalese productions.

The degree to which the "Gupta" style characteristics are manifest in these images is roughly similar to that of the Madras Museum bronze Buddha of 700 A.D. They may all, therefore, be dated in the first half of the eighth century.

The "Gupta" style characteristics are more

fully realized in the Aukana Buddha and the date of that image must be a little later. The peculiar formula used for defining the drapery folds at Aukana is anticipated in the drapery patterns of a limestone torso in the Colombo Museum (Fig. 11). In this image, the system of ridges representing the gathers of cloth recalls the same device used in the bronzes of Dong Duong, Korat and the Madras Museum discussed above, but the intervals have already started to become concavities. This fact, together with that of the greater form definition of the anatomy shown through the garment, determines for the limestone torso, a date closer to the Aukana colossus.

The same may be said of the metal Buddha image found, in 1961, near the railway station at Medavachchiya.³³ This image (Fig. 12) approximates, in every way and including the hand positions, the style and appearance of the great icon at Aukana. If the treatment of the drapery in the small metal image suggests a date earlier than that of the rock-cut example, it cannot be far away in time.

The sculptural convention for defining the drapery of the Aukana Buddha is exactly repeated in a number of smaller stone Buddha images, which also manifest the other qualities of its style, and must be dated with it in the second half of the eighth century.

Fig. 12. Bronze Buddha image from Medavachchiya.

Fig. 13. Stone Buddha image at the Mahābhūpa, Anurādhapura.

Fig. 14. Bronze Buddha image from Kankanodai.

The best known of this group is the standing Buddha (Fig. 13), carved from limestone, and once placed on the terrace of the Ruanveli Dāgoba at the Mahāvihāra. It has normally been given to the early period, but its pronounced likeness to the style of the Aukana Buddha demonstrates that the third to fourth century date given it by Coomaraswamy³⁴ is much too early.

Two standing Buddha images, found in a cave at Budu-galge, near Badulla, and now in the Anurādhapura Museum, may also be included in this group.

Some images may be associated with the Aukana colossus from the point of view of general stylistic character, but for other reasons must be slightly later in date. The bronze Buddha from Kankanodai, Batticaloa (Fig. 14) looks in every way a miniature replica of the Aukana Buddha, but the developed character of the *siris-pota*, with its tiny gem-setting suggests a date in the ninth century rather than the eighth.

The nine-foot stone Buddha,³⁵ now in the Ata-dā-gē, in Polonnaruva, betrays the same sculptural form and scooped drapery convention of the late eighth century style. However, it shows the exaggerated slenderness of the Kankanodai bronze and the hairline is rendered in a pronounced double curve, a feature which seems to be more characteristic of later images.

The same type of stylized hair line is found on the colossal Buddha of Sesseruva, (Fig. 5) where the scooped drapery technique has given way to a kind of ineffectual grooving of diagonal lines. Otherwise, what we have in this giant figure is a rather close copy of its fellow at Aukana. We may assign to it, somewhat arbitrarily, a ninth or even tenth century date.

The establishment of a distinct style-category of standing Buddha image and the fixing, for its development, of a date in the eighth century, provides for us a useful measuring stick by means of which we may date other Buddha images, not necessarily standing.

Two bronze Buddhas, shown seated, in the collection of the Colombo Museum, may be dated with the Buddhas of the first half of the eighth century. The well-known damaged figure from Badulla (Fig. 15), gesturing the *vitarka mudrā* with the right hand and grasping the lap-pet of the robe with the left, recalls the Madras Museum bronze of ca. 700 A.D. The drapery, represented by a series of undulating ridges, confirms the suggestion of a date in the early part of the eighth century.

The other bronze (Fig. 16), given by Bell to the Colombo Museum, bears a striking resemblance to the Korat image. The drapery, however, is defined by a peculiar convention of

Fig. 15. Bronze Buddha image from Badulla.

grouping double incised lines at regular intervals. It is as though the system, shown in the Korat and Dong Duong examples, of grouping ridges and incised lines to suggest the rise and fall of the stuff, had been condensed into a linear pattern.³⁶

A stone torso of a seated Buddha (Fig. 17), now placed against a banyan tree on the grounds of the Anurādhapura Museum, displays the scooped drapery treatment in the rendition of its garment; the ridges and concavities merge, however, into smoothness at the knees. The line of the undergarment and the soft bulge of the flesh above it, are clearly shown. We may date this image in the second half of the eighth century along with what appears to be its replica in bronze (Fig. 18), a small Buddha seated in the Dhyāna position and found at the Tolvila *pilima-ge* in Anurādhapura. Its date in the latter half of the eighth century, arrived at on the basis of other qualities of its style, is confirmed by the depiction of the hem of the *uttarāsanga* running from the shoulder down to the lap, across the wrist and thigh, and behind to the double-lotus throne.

The identification of the Colossal Buddha of Aukana as a Mahāyāna icon, the fixing of its date in the second half of the eighth century, and the formal and symbolic association of it with a substantial number of other Buddha images, has

Fig. 16. Bronze Buddha image in the Colombo Museum.

Fig. 17. Stone torso at the Anurādhapura Museum.

enabled us (1) to establish a distinct iconographical type among Sinhalese Buddha images and (2) to determine the chronological and stylistic sequence of a class of them ranging in time from the seventh century to the tenth.

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- 1, 2, 3, 17: photos by D. K. Dohanian.
- 4, 7, 8, 9: Archaeological Survey of Ceylon.
- 5, 13: from negatives once belonging to A. K. Coomaraswamy now at R.A.R.B., Fogg Art Museum.
- 11: from *Ceylon Journal of Science*, Section G, II, plate XII, fig. 2.
- 12: from *Artibus Asiae*, vol. xxvi, ¾, Godakumbura, plate 1, facing p. 230.
- 10: from D. T. Devendra, *Classical Sinhalese Sculpture*, fig. 72.
- 14, 15, 16, 18: from Devendra, *The Buddha Image and Ceylon*, figures XIII, XIV, XVII, XVIII.
- 6: from ASIAR, 1908-09, Plate XXVIII, d.

NOTES

1. *Archaeological Survey of Ceylon, Annual Report, 1955*, p. 24.
2. Colossal images, carved from stone and built of brick, are found at ancient sites all over Ceylon. In the ninth and tenth centuries, a recumbent colossus was a regular feature of the monastery plan. In the great image-houses of Polonnaruva, towering Buddhas of brick and stucco dominated the interiors.
3. The idea that the Buddha is in his secret essence transcendent and beyond the spheres of the world was the seed concept from which the theology of the Mahāyāna grew. In time, the increasing pre-occupation of Mahāyāna art and thought was with the development of techniques and instruments with which to realize the fact of the Buddha's transcendental perfection. One of the most straightforward and compelling of these instruments was the iconic image of spectacular size.
4. W. Rahula, *History of Buddhism in Ceylon*, (Colombo, 1956), p. 88; A. Bareau, *Les Sectes Bouddhiques du Petit Véhicule* (Saigon 1955) p. 254.
5. *ASC,AR, 1934*, pp. 21-22; *ASC,AR, 1951*, p. 37.
6. Parānavitana, in H. C. Ray (ed.) *History of Ceylon*, I, 1, p. 404, has identified the monastery tentatively as the "Image Monastery" built by Prince Aggabodhi of Rohana, about 600 A.D. In that case, the ruined stone colossus would be the earliest known colossal image of the Buddha in Ceylon.
7. *ASC,AR, 1946*, pp. 13ff.
8. *ASC,AR, 1926-27*, pp. 6, 7; *ASC,AR, 1934*, p. 8; S. Parānavitana, "Recent Archaeological Work in Ceylon", *Indian Art and Letters*, XI, 1, 1937, p. 27.
9. Height, 42 feet 8 inches. The *mudrās* are the same as those in the Aukana image with the exception that the *abbaya mudrā* is performed with the palm facing out. The front of the image has been sheared off and very little remains of the original surface of the face.
10. The date of the Buduruwegala carving has been determined as the second half of the tenth century. See D. K. Dohanian, "The Mahāyāna Buddhist Sculpture of Ceylon", unpublished doctoral dissertation (Harvard 1964) p. 89.
11. *ASC,AR, 1895*, p. 12.
12. I use the term "medieval" to refer to the seventh through the tenth centuries, which period of time links the last gasp of Ceylon's "classical" era with the great "renaissance" under the Polonnaruva sovereigns.
13. *Ibid.* p. 6, 7.
14. p. 76.
15. V. Smith, *A History of Fine Arts in India and Ceylon*, second edition (Oxford, 1930), p. 150.
16. Viśvakarma (London 1914). In *History of Indian and Indonesian Art* (London 1927), p. 165, he places it in the twelfth century.
17. *ASC,AR, 1949*, pp. 18-19.
18. *Mahāvamsa* 38:42. No mention is made of an image.
19. *ASC,AR, 1952*, p. 33.
20. *loc.cit.*
21. The fleshiness of the form, the crisp, sharp edges on the details of the face, the shape of the body manifest through the *uttarāśaṅga*, the accented swell of the belly and the sharp depression which cuts across the waist to suggest the tie of the undergarment.
22. B. Rowland, *The Art and Architecture of India* (Baltimore and Harmondsworth 1953), plate 137 (A).
23. It is questionable whether the head belongs to this image.
24. D. Barrett, "The Later School of Amarāvātī and its Influences", *Art and Letters*, XXVIII, 2, 1954, pp. 41-53.
25. *ASI,AR, 1908-09*, plate XXVIII, a and b.
26. R. Sewell, "Some Buddhist Bronzes and Relics of the Buddha", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 1895, pp. 617-637, plates I and II. The example in the Boston Museum of Fine Arts, #21.1504, is shown in Coomaraswamy, *History of Indian and Indonesian Art*, plate XL, 159.
27. *ASC,AR, 1951*, p. 26.
28. On the image to the left, the drapery folds were indicated by rounded grooves, close and regularly placed. The form

Fig. 18. Bronze Buddha image from Toluville.

- is elongated and the head smallish. There is an exaggerated swing to the torso contour and also in the curve of the garment from the swag to the left arm. The image on the right seems archaic. The facial type, however, corresponds to the twelfth century carvings at Gal-vihāra, Polonnaruva.
29. The head has been re-cut and the bottom is restored.
 30. Rowland, *op.cit.*, plate 137 (B).
 31. P. DuPont, *L'archéologie Mène de Dvāravātī* (Paris 1959), plate 92, figure 336.
 32. These have been a puzzle to scholars for a long time. They are discussed in the following, where differing opinions have been expressed: G. Coedes, *Les états hindouisés d'Indochine et d'Indonésie (Histoire du Monde, VIII, Paris 1948)*, pp. 37-39; M. L. D'Ancona "Amarāvātī, Ceylon, and Three 'Imported Bronzes'", *Art Bulletin*, XXXIV, 1, 1952, pp. 1-17; P. DuPont, "Les Buddhas dits d'Amarāvātī en Asie du Sud-Est", *Bulletin de l'École Française d'Extrême Orient*, XLIX, 2, 1959, pp. 631-636; R. LeMay, *A Concise History of Buddhist Art in Siam*, (Cambridge 1938), p. 16, and *Annual Bibliography of Indian Archaeology, 1933*, VIII, p. 35.
 33. C. E. Godakumbura, "A Bronze Buddha Image from Ceylon", *Artibus Asiae*, vol. XXVI, ¾, pp. 230-236. In this extended note on the find, the image is dated in the third to fourth centuries.
 34. Coomaraswamy, A., *History of Indian and Indonesian Art*, p. 161.
 35. Ray, *op.cit.*, I, 2, plate XXXIX (a).
 36. If we consider the vestigial *sirispota*, on this image and the one from Korat, as an indication of a later date, then we might have to reassign them to the latter part of the eighth century. The *sirispota* is a troublesome detail in the Buddhist imagery of this time, for although it is a constant feature in images of a later date, we have no real idea of the time of its first appearance in the iconography of the Buddha image. These small bronzes may, in fact, represent the moment of the introduction of this feature into the symbolic fabric of the Buddha image. But, even if we accept this notion, we cannot say for sure whether that time was before or after the middle of the eighth century.